

1 DOES PERCEPTUAL GROUPING IMPROVE
2 VISUOSPATIAL WORKING MEMORY? OPTIMIZED
3 PROCESSING OR ENCODING BIAS

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41 experiment design and programming, data collection, data analysis, manuscript
42 reviewing. Julia Mayas: manuscript reviewing.

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Abstract

56 Visual working memory has been defined as a system of limited capacity that allows the
57 maintenance and manipulation of visual information. However, some perceptual
58 features like Gestalt grouping could improve visual working memory effectiveness. In
59 two different experiments, we aimed to explore how the presence of elements grouped
60 by color similarity affects the change detection performance of both, grouped and non-
61 grouped items. We combined a change detection task with a retrocue paradigm in which
62 a 6-item array had to be remembered. An always valid, variable-delay retrocue appeared
63 in some trials during the retention interval, either after 100 ms (iconic-trace period) or
64 1400 ms (working memory period), signaling the location of the probe. The results
65 indicated that similarity grouping biased the information entered into the visual working
66 memory, improving change detection accuracy only for previously grouped probes, but
67 hindering change detection for non-grouped probes in certain conditions (Exp. 1).
68 However, this bottom-up automatic encoding bias was overridden when participants
69 were explicitly instructed to ignore grouped items as they were irrelevant for the task
70 (Exp. 2).

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79 **1. Introduction**

80 Visual working memory (VWM) is a temporary buffer capable of actively store, process
81 and manipulate the information coming from the visual world (Logie, 1986; Luck &
82 Vogel, 2013). However, VWM is severely restricted in terms of capacity, with estimates
83 converging on a limit of 3-4 items stored simultaneously (e.g. Alvarez & Cavanagh,
84 2004; Awh et al., 2007; Fukuda et al., 2010; Luck & Vogel, 1997). These capacity
85 constraints lead to two different questions: First, can these storage limits be exceeded?
86 And second, if so, what factors may contribute to increasing the capacity of VWM?
87 Behavioral, neurophysiological and even daily-life evidence has shown that VWM
88 capacity limits can be surpassed. Moreover, several cognitive (e.g. long-term memory
89 aid, familiarity, attentional selection) and perceptual factors seem to affect VWM
90 capacity (Brady et al., 2016; Heuer & Schubö, 2016; Jackson & Raymond, 2008; Qian
91 et al., 2017). Within the last ones, perceptual organization cues and particularly the
92 Gestalt grouping principles (e.g. similarity, proximity, closure, common fate,
93 continuity) have been a prolific area of interest (Palmer, 2003; Pomerantz & Kubovy,
94 1981; Wagemans, 2016). These organizational cues are known to improve perceptual
95 performance (see Wagemans et al., 2012 for an extensive review; Wertheimer, 1923) by
96 parsing the visual scene into component objects according to certain rules (Duncan,
97 1984; Duncan & Humphreys, 1989; Kahneman & Henik, 1977; Moore & Egeth, 1997).
98 Particularly, perceptual grouping seems to parse the visual scene at a preattentive stage
99 of visual processing and organizes the visual information before other cognitive
100 processes have access to it (Lamy et al., 2006; Mack et al., 1992). Nonetheless, even if
101 grouping occurs pre or even inattentively, attention is needed for the items to access and
102 be encoded into the working memory (Moore & Egeth, 1997). Given that, it would be

103 not surprising if this early organization of the visual information could improve
104 information processing (Woodman et al., 2003) leading to an increase in VWM
105 performance, but the critical question is whether this early organization of the visual
106 information also unintentionally biases the allocation of attentional resources over the
107 items to be memorized (Duncan, 1984; Qian et al., 2020).

108 There is consistent evidence of improved VWM performance when the items to be
109 remembered can be linked by the presence of different grouping cues (e.g. Allon et al.,
110 2019; Gao et al., 2016; Peterson et al., 2015; Peterson & Berryhill, 2013; Woodman et
111 al., 2003; Xu & Chun, 2007; Zhang et al., 2016; but see Li et al., 2018 for a review of
112 grouping effects on VWM). For example, Woodman et al. (2003) using a pre-cued
113 change detection task (CDT), found that grouping the items through spatial proximity
114 improved VWM performance. Their results showed that items grouped tend to be stored
115 together even if they were not directly cued. The grouping principle of similarity has
116 also been widely studied in the context of VWM benefits. In two different studies,
117 Peterson & Berryhill (2013) and Peterson et al. (2015) found that color similarity
118 increased VWM performance in a classical CDT. Other grouping principles like
119 closure, connectedness and collinearity have also proven effective in improving the
120 performance of VWM, but the effects sizes obtained are significantly lower than those
121 obtained in studies that employed the grouping principles of proximity and similarity
122 (Gao et al., 2016).

123 Although there is compelling evidence on the effects of perceptual grouping over VWM
124 performance, the mechanisms behind this effect are less clear. One possibility is that
125 perceptual grouping only serves as a mean to organize visual information, allowing
126 multiple individual items that share common features (like some grouping principles) to
127 be treated as a single unit in memory or a “chunk”, a form of lossless compression that

128 leads to more efficient processing of the information (Brady et al., 2009; Corbett, 2017;
129 Nassar et al., 2018; Zhang & Luck, 2011). This would allow more items to be stored by
130 freeing up resources that can be reallocated to other items (e.g. Bays & Husain, 2008),
131 or by using fewer slots for the same amount of information. In agreement with this
132 account of grouping effects, Kałamała et al. (2017) found that the total number of
133 objects maintained in VWM (k value) was greater when some of the items to be
134 remembered were grouped by whole-part similarity. Moreover, Peterson et al. (2015),
135 found that benefits to VWM derived from different grouping principles (similarity,
136 proximity and connectedness) were echoed by a reduction of contralateral delay activity
137 (CDA) amplitude, a result that can be interpreted in terms of a reduction of the
138 resources devoted to VWM. On the other hand, the improvement in VWM performance
139 could be derived from an encoding bias towards the grouped items (Li et al., 2018;
140 Peterson & Berryhill, 2013). According to this account, the VWM improvement would
141 result from the preattentive processing of grouping cues and the object-based (or
142 feature-based) attentional capture provoked by the grouped elements (Treisman, 1982;
143 Vecera, 1994; Vecera & Farah, 1994). This will result in a better encoding of the
144 grouped items into the VWM at the expense of a poor encoding of the non-grouped
145 items, especially when the number of items exceeds the VWM capacity (Awh et al.,
146 2006). In support of this explanation, Peterson & Berryhill (2013) found that the VWM
147 was restricted to probed items that were grouped during stimulus presentation,
148 suggesting a bias toward encoding the grouped items. Moreover, Qian et al. (2020)
149 using a pre-cued CDT paradigm, showed that certain features (such as color) guide the
150 attention in a mandatory and automatic manner, leading to a memory benefit for the
151 items that shared this feature. Finally, in a recent meta-analytic study, Li et al. (2018)
152 provided a tentative explanation for the mechanisms behind the effect of grouping on

153 the VWM. These authors argued that the grouping effect seems to depend on the
154 grouping relevancy of the tested feature. Specifically, the authors suggest that when the
155 tested feature is grouping relevant (as is the case of our study), the feature is processed
156 first to form perceptual grouping, and its storage will not involve competing for
157 attention or memory resources as grouping seems to occur at a preattentive stage
158 (Duncan & Humphreys, 1989; Mack et al., 1992). However, if an irrelevant feature is
159 tested, storage for that feature should occur after the perceptual group is perceived and
160 the items will compete with the others to obtain better storage. In this case, irrelevant
161 features will obtain attentional priority in the encoding stage due to their belonging to
162 the grouped items (Fine & Minnery, 2009; Melcher & Piazza, 2011).

163 Given the mixed evidence found in the previous literature regarding the nature of the
164 VWM improvements, the present study aims to explore the mechanisms that underlie
165 the VWM improvement associated with perceptual grouping and, especially, the role
166 that attentional processes play in it when grouping-relevant features are tested. We
167 focused on two possible accounts for this beneficial effect. The first is a “chunking”
168 process that compresses grouped items into a single “chunk” of information. This
169 hypothesis states that grouping allows more efficient processing of the items to be
170 remembered without compromising attentional resources, so more resources would be
171 available to store the relevant information (Corbett, 2017). Conversely, the “encoding
172 bias” hypothesis states that the presence of grouping cues is processed pre-attentively at
173 the early stages of the perceptual stream, and automatically directs feature-based
174 attention to the grouped elements (Duncan, 1984; Qian et al., 2020; Vecera, 1994)
175 during the memory task. This last approach leads to an attentional encoding bias that
176 would impair the encoding of the non-grouped items into the VWM. To this end, we
177 combined a classical CDT and the use of a variable-delay retrocue paradigm to direct

178 the attention to specific item locations within the internal representations of the items
179 stored in the VWM.

180 To this end, we conducted two experiments in which an array of 6 colored items were
181 presented briefly at six different locations. In Experiment 1, the participants were
182 instructed to memorize all the items until the appearance of a probe which could either
183 have the same or different color (see Rensink, 2002 for a thorough review on change
184 detection theoretical basis and methodologies). Two critical manipulations were added
185 to the main task: 1) in some trials two of the items of the memory array shared the same
186 color (grouped by color similarity), and 2) three different endogenous retrocues
187 conditions with variable delays were included. As previous literature indicates that the
188 benefit of perceptual grouping occurs at the encoding stage of the VWM (Li et al.,
189 2018), we expect different effects depending on the delay of the retrocues. In the short-
190 retrocues condition, the retrocues appear while the iconic-memory trace of the array
191 persists (Becker et al., 2000; Gegenfurtner & Sperling, 1993; Sperling, 1960). Thus, we
192 expect similar facilitation in the change detection task for any cued item, regardless of
193 whether it was or not previously grouped, as all the information of the memory array
194 will be still available independently of the attentional resources allocated to each item.

195 In the long-retrocue condition, the retrocues appear after the iconic memory trace has
196 vanished and the array to be remembered is already encoded in the VWM. If grouping
197 not only organizes the visual scene but also induces an attentional encoding bias
198 towards grouped items, then we expect the retrocues to have different effects depending
199 on the items cued. In this case, grouped items will be better encoded and less prone to
200 decay over time as more attentional resources would be allocated to them. This would
201 result in the cue being more effective for the grouped items.

202 In Experiment 2 participants were instructed to ignore the items that shared the same
203 color (grouped items), as they will not be probed in the CDT. This will allow us to test
204 if an encoding bias towards grouped items can be counteracted by top-down voluntary
205 processes that filter out irrelevant information according to the goals of the task or, on
206 the contrary, grouped items can capture attention irrespective of the task demands. The
207 rationale for this experiment was twofold. First, according to our encoding bias
208 hypothesis, it would be interesting to address how the task demands could affect the
209 capacity of the grouped items to bias the encoding of non grouped items and, therefore,
210 memory performance. Second, there is conflicting evidence in the previous literature
211 regarding whether perceptual grouping enhances or hinders the inhibition of irrelevant
212 information. On one side, Kimchi et al. (2007, 2016) found that perceptual grouping can
213 capture attention irrespective of task demands, leading to full processing of irrelevant
214 items and hindering the inhibition of non-relevant information. A similar result was
215 obtained by Zupan & Watson (2020) who found that perceptual grouping reduced the
216 number of distractors that can be inhibited. On the other hand, Allon et al. (2019)
217 showed that grouping by spatial proximity and the presence of illusory objects (another
218 form of perceptual organization) improved filtering performance when the grouped
219 items acted as distractors. However, given that different grouping principles are thought
220 to have different processing demands (Driver et al., 2001; Kimchi & Razpurker-Apfeld,
221 2004) and participants are forced to attend and process the grouped stimuli to filter them
222 out (as grouping is the key feature that distinguishes relevant from irrelevant items), it is
223 not clear whether the similarity cues employed in the present study will lead to a better
224 or worse filtering performance.

225 To sum up, in Experiment 1 we expect to find: 1) a general improvement in change
226 detection accuracy in trials in which part of the items of the memory array are grouped

227 through color similarity. 2) According to the encoding bias hypothesis, we expect that
228 this improvement will only occur when the items probed were previously grouped in the
229 memory array, and no benefit or even a worsening effect will appear when the probes
230 were non-grouped items of a grouped memory array. 3) We also hypothesized that the
231 non-grouped items will be more affected by the delay of the retrocue, due to the worse
232 encoding and the increased susceptibility to decay over time. In Experiment 2 we
233 hypothesized that, according to previous results in space-based presentations (Allon et
234 al., 2019), participants will be able to counteract the attentional capture generated by
235 grouped items and filter them out as they are irrelevant for the task. This will lead to an
236 opposite pattern of results compared to Experiment 1, with better performance in
237 change detection in those arrays that contain grouped elements (4 relevant elements)
238 compared with arrays that do not contain grouped elements (6 relevant elements).

239 **2. Experiment 1**

240 In Experiment 1 we aimed to investigate the effect of an always valid retrocue presented
241 at different latencies over the recognition of the elements of a memory array that could
242 be all of different color or contain two adjacent items grouped by color similarity. We
243 employed a change detection task (Pashler, 1988) in which participants were asked to
244 indicate if the element presented as a probe was the same or different color as the
245 element that appeared at the same position in the memory array.

246 **2.1. Methods**

247 *2.1.1. Participants*

248 Sixty-two undergraduate students (fourteen males; age range: 18-51, mean age = 28.6;
249 SD = 9.5) at the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) participated
250 in this experiment as part of a practical course. Fifty-seven were right-handed and all of
251 them had either normal or correct-to-normal visual acuity and color vision. The results

252 of the a priori power analysis indicated that a minimum sample size of 54 participants
253 was necessary to achieve a power of .80 given an effect size of $f = .20$ (medium). The
254 study was conducted following the Declaration of Helsinki and it was approved by the
255 Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia Ethics Committee. Written informed
256 consent was obtained before the beginning of the study.

257 2.1.2. *Stimuli and apparatus*

258 The stimuli consisted of six colored circles subtending 2.8° of visual angle (VA) each
259 made with Microsoft Paint software. The stimuli were arranged in a circular
260 configuration (8.5° VA from the center of the screen to the center of each circle). Six
261 colour categories were used: red (R: 255; G: 0; B: 0), yellow (R: 255; G: 255; B: 0),
262 green (R: 0; G: 255; B: 0), blue (R: 0; G: 0; B: 255), cyan (R: 0; G: 255; B: 255) and
263 magenta (R: 255; G: 0; B: 255). These colors were combined to form two different
264 types of arrays: 1) grouped arrays containing two adjacent circles that share the same
265 color and four circles of different colors; 2) non-grouped arrays in which all six circles
266 had a different color. The color distribution and the position of the pairs of grouped
267 stimuli in the arrays were randomly selected. The retrocue consisted of an arrow
268 subtending 1.4° VA whose base was located at the center of the screen. The probe was a
269 single colored circle of the same dimensions as the ones presented previously and
270 placed randomly in one of the six possible locations of the array. The experiment was
271 programmed using E-Prime2 (Psychology Software Tools) and displayed on an LCD-
272 IPS 24-inch widescreen monitor with a refresh rate of 75 Hz and a resolution of 1280 x
273 720 pixels. The viewing distance was kept constant at 60 cm.

274 2.1.3. *Design and Procedure*

275 A repeated measures design with the within-subject factors: *retrocue latency* (short,
276 long, non-cue), *type of array* (grouped array[GA], non-grouped array [NGA]) and *probe*

277 *grouping* (grouped [GP], non-grouped [NGP]) was employed. The design was not
278 completely factorial, as the grouped probes were only possible within the context of
279 arrays that contained grouped elements. The task consisted of a variant of the classic
280 change detection paradigm in which an always valid variable-delay retrocue, indicated
281 the item to be remembered in some of the trials (see Fig. 1).

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283 **Fig. 1** *Experimental sequence in Experiments 1 and 2*

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289 Participants were tested in individual cabins of our laboratory. The task consisted of
290 indicating, as fast and accurate as possible, whether the color of the probe matched the
291 one positioned at the same location in the memory array (50% chance). Each trial began
292 with the appearance of two digits (500 ms) that the participants must repeat aloud
293 throughout the trial to avoid the verbal encoding of the colors and spatial locations that
294 compounded the stimulus array (Matsukura & Vecera, 2015). After the offset of the two
295 digits, a fixation cross appeared in the center of the screen (1000 ms) to ensure the
296 central fixation of the eye gaze followed by the memory array (200 ms). After the
297 disappearance of the memory array, an arrow indicating the position of the item that
298 will be probed (retrocue) could appear at two different delays: in the *short-latency*
299 condition, the retrocue was presented 100 ms after the memory array (ISI 1) and
300 disappeared 1800 ms before the onset of the probe (ISI 2); in the *long latency* condition,
301 the retrocue appeared 1400 ms after the memory array and disappeared 500 ms before
302 the onset of the probe. Finally, in the *no-retrocue* condition, the same grey background

303 was presented until the appearance of the probe. In all retrocue latency conditions, the
304 retrocue remained in the computer screen for 100 ms (or only the grey background in
305 the no-retrocue condition), so in all trials the time between the offset of the memory
306 array and the onset of the probe was kept constant at 2000 ms. Finally, the probe was
307 presented until the participant performed a response. Each retrocue latency condition
308 represented 1/3 of the total trials. Participants were instructed to answer, as accurately
309 and fast as possible, whether the color of the probe matched the one at the same location
310 in the memory array (forced-choice response). The participants responded by pressing
311 the “1” and “2” keys of the numeric keyboard. Half of the trials were “same” trials in
312 which the probe had the same color as the item at the same location in the memory
313 array, the other half were “different” trials, in which the probe color was different from
314 the item at the same location in the memory array. Before the start of the experiment,
315 participants performed an 8-trial practice block in which participants received feedback
316 about their performance. The experiment consisted of 360 trials divided into two blocks
317 of 180 trials with a short break between them. The total number of trials per condition
318 was the same for all conditions and set to 40 (20 per block). All the experimental
319 conditions were randomly presented, and response keys were counterbalanced across
320 participants. No feedback about the accuracy of the responses was given during
321 experimental trials.

322 **2.2. Results**

323 Trials with reaction times (RTs) below 200 ms and those above/below 2.5 standard
324 deviations of the mean were rejected before entering the accuracy analysis. In RT
325 analysis trials with RTs above 2500 ms were also rejected. Statistical analyses were
326 performed using repeated measures ANOVAs and posthoc comparisons when necessary
327 (Bonferroni corrected). RTs and accuracy (% correct) were taken as dependent variables

328 (Cowan, 2010; Peterson & Berryhill, 2013). The design of the experiment was not
329 completely factorial as probes in non-grouped arrays (NGA) could only be non-
330 grouped, so we performed a 3 x 3 repeated-measures ANOVA with the within-subjects
331 factors *retrocue latency* (short, long, no-retrocue) and *probe type* (NGA, GA/GP;
332 GA/NGP).

333 2.2.1. Accuracy (% correct)

334 The results of the ANOVA showed a significant main effect of the factor *probe type* F
335 $(2,60) = 264.07; p < .001; \eta^2p = .812; \beta = 1$. Post-hoc Pairwise comparisons showed
336 that GP were better recognized (92,7%; all $ps < 0.01$) than NGP, whether they came
337 from NGA arrays or from GA arrays (81,6% vs 80,.8% respectively; $p = 0.26$). The
338 main effect of *retrocue latency* also reached statistical significance $F (2,60) = 328.52; p$
339 $< .001; \eta^2p = .843; \beta = 1$. Pairwise comparisons indicated that the performance in the
340 change detection task was maximal after short retrocue trials (94.3%), followed by long
341 retrocue trials (85.4%) and no retrocue trials (75.3.8%) respectively (all p 's $< .001$).
342 Finally, these effects were qualified by a significant *retrocue latency x probe type*
343 interaction $F (4,58) = 33.26; p < .001; \eta^2p = .353; \beta = 1$. Post hoc comparisons showed
344 that NGP in NGA were better recognized compared with NGP in GA but only in the
345 long retrocue condition (82.9% vs 79.8%; $p = 0.014$). In addition, recognition
346 performance for GP was better compared to NGP in all retrocue conditions (all $ps <$
347 0.001).Second, to analyze the effect of the different retrocue conditions over grouped
348 and non-grouped probes, we computed a differential variable by subtracting accuracy
349 for GP and accuracy for NGP (in both GA and NGA) in each retrocue condition
350 [Accuracy GP – Accuracy NGP]. The one-way ANOVA performed on this variable
351 showed a main effect of *retrocue condition* $F (2,60) = 78.51; p < .001; \eta^2p = .563; \beta =$
352 1. Pairwise multiple comparisons indicated that the recognition advantage for GP

353 increased as a function of retrocue latency (all $ps < 0.001$), with the short-latency
354 leading to the smallest difference (4.4%), followed by the long latency condition
355 (12.1%) and no-retrocue condition (18.0%). An overview of the results is shown in Fig.
356 2.

357 **Fig. 2** Accuracy for GP and NGP in both NGA and GA as a function of retrocue
358 condition (a). Accuracy differences between grouped and non-grouped probes as a
359 function of retrocue condition (b)

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371 Accuracy (% correct) for GP and NGP (left), and differences in accuracy for GP and
372 NGP (right) in the three retrocue conditions. NGP: non-grouped probes, GP: grouped
373 probes. The error bars represent 1 SEM.

374 Last, to analyze the cueing benefits of short and long retrocues in each probe type
375 (NGP, GP), we performed an additional ANOVA in Experiment 1 by computing a new
376 differential variable that accounts for cueing benefits (the performance difference
377 between valid and no retrocue conditions) for GP and NGP separately. We made this by
378 subtracting the recognition performance in no-retrocue condition from short and long
379 retrocue conditions respectively. Then we performed a *3-probe type* (NGP-NGA, NGP-
380 GA, GP-GA) x *2-cueing benefit* (short-no, long-no) repeated measures ANOVA. The
381 results showed a main effect of the factor cueing benefit $F(1,61) = 181.73; p < .001;$
382 $\eta^2p = .749; \beta = 1$, indicating that the cueing benefit was higher with short delays of the
383 retrocue (19% vs 10%). The main effect of probe type was also significant $F(2,60) =$
384 $32.82; p < .001; \eta^2p = .350; \beta = 1$. Pairwise comparisons showed that cueing benefits
385 for NGP were larger than for GP ($p < .001$). More interesting, the first-order interaction

386 between cueing benefit and probe type also reached significance $F(2,60) = 34.09$; $p <$
387 $.001$; $\eta^2p = .358$; $\beta = 1$. A closer look at this interaction reveals that while short
388 retrocues are equally effective for NGP in both NGA and GA, long retrocues are more
389 effective for NGP when the array did not contain grouped items (NGA), compared to
390 arrays that contained grouped items (GA) $p = .004$. The results of this analysis are
391 summarized in Fig.3.

392 **Fig. 3** Cueing benefits in performance as a function of probe type

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400 Benefits (%) of cueing (short and long delay) for NGA-NGP, GA-NGP and GA-GP
401 (left). The error bars represent 1 SEM.

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403 2.2.2. Reaction times

404 The analysis of the response times followed the same structure depicted in the accuracy
405 analysis. We performed a 3x3 repeated measures ANOVA, with *retrocue latency* (short,
406 long, no-retrocue) and *probe type* (NGA, GA/GP; GA/NGP) as within-subjects factors.
407 The results showed a significant main effect of *probe type* $F(2,60) = 103.48$; $p < .001$;
408 $\eta^2p = .629$; $\beta = 1$. Pairwise comparisons indicated that the responses for GP (746 ms)
409 were faster than the responses for NGP (all $ps < 0.001$) regardless of whether they came
410 from arrays with grouped items or not (833 ms and 821 ms respectively). The main
411 effect of *retrocue latency* was also significant $F(2,60) = 630.46$; $p < .001$; $\eta^2p = .912$; β
412 $= 1$. Pairwise comparisons indicated that the responses in the change detection task were
413 faster after short retrocue trials (640 ms), followed by long retrocue trials (745 ms) and
414 no retrocue trials (1016 ms), with all $p's < .001$. Finally, the *retrocue latency x probe-*
415 *type* interaction also reached statistical significance $F(4,58) = 8.32$; $p < .001$; $\eta^2p =$

416 .120; $\beta = .997$. Post-hoc comparisons revealed that the RTs for NGP in NGA were
 417 lower than RTs for NGP in GA, but only in the *no retrocue* condition ($p = .004$). No
 418 other effects reached statistical significance. A summary of the RT results is shown in
 419 Table 1.

420 **Table 1.** Experiment 1 mean response times (SD) as a function of the type of array,
 421 probe grouping and retrocue latency.

		Array type		
		GA		NGA
Retrocue latency	Probe	NGP	GP	NGP
	Short	652 (153)	637 (199)	654 (155)
	Long	781 (190)	699 (202)	769 (180)
	No	1056 (215)	989 (241)	1028 (204)

422 GA: grouped array; NGA: non-grouped array; NGP: non-grouped probe; GP: grouped
 423 probe. All response times are expressed in ms.

424 **2.3. Interim discussion**

425 The results of the first experiment indicated that Gestalt grouping by color similarity
 426 generally improves accuracy and RTs in a change detection task, a result that agrees
 427 with the results obtained previously in the literature (see Li et al., 2018). However, this
 428 effect seems to differ significantly between retrocue conditions and grouped/non-
 429 grouped probes. First, participants performed much better in the CDT when the probed
 430 items were previously grouped in the memory array, suggesting that the VWM benefit
 431 associated with grouping is restricted to those items. Second, the effect of the retrocue
 432 conditions was different between GP and NGP (see Fig. 2b). In short retrocue trials,
 433 although performance for GP was higher, NGP almost matched them. However, the
 434 difference in performance between GP and NGP became larger as the retrocue increased
 435 in latency or if it did not even appear. Last, performance for NGP was not improved by
 436 the presence of grouped items. Instead, in the long retrocue condition, performance for
 437 NGP worsened in GA compared to NGA trials and remained equal in the rest of the
 438 conditions. The RTs analysis mirrored this pattern of results, showing faster RTs in
 439 those conditions where participants were more accurate (see Table 1).

440 To sum up, three different findings support the encoding bias hypothesis in Experiment
441 1. First, we found a general improvement in change detection accuracy when some of
442 the items in the memory array were grouped, but this benefit was restricted to GP.
443 Second, the advantage for GP became smaller as the retrocue reduced its latency. Third,
444 the presence of GP in the memory array did not improve recognition performance for
445 NGP (or even worsened it depending on the conditions).

446 **3. Experiment 2**

447 Overall, the results from Experiment 1, suggest that the VWM improvement found
448 when the memory array contained grouped items is not caused only by a chunking
449 process or the optimized organization of the information (that reduces the number of
450 effective elements to be encoded), but by the automatic attentional capture produced by
451 the grouped elements which, in turn, can hinder the encoding of the remaining items in
452 the VWM (Awh et al., 2006; Edward Awh & Jonides, 2001; Treisman, 1982).

453 In Experiment 2, we explore if this grouping-directed encoding bias can be overridden
454 by the voluntary allocation of attentional resources that simultaneously select task-
455 relevant and filter out irrelevant information (Allon et al., 2019; Allon & Luria, 2017; Li
456 et al., 2017; Sawaki & Luck, 2010, 2011). To this end, we employed the same task and
457 experimental design described in Experiment 1, but this time the grouped elements
458 served as distractors, and participants were explicitly instructed to ignore them as they
459 will not be tested in the CDT.

460 **3.1. Methods**

461 *3.1.1. Participants*

462 Forty undergraduate students (ten males; age range: 18-57, mean age = 25.05; SD =
463 9.92) at the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) participated in this
464 experiment as part of practices credits. Thirty-seven were right-handed and all of them

465 had either normal or corrected-to-normal visual acuity and color vision. The results of
466 the a priori power analysis indicated that a minimum sample size of 42 participants was
467 necessary to achieve a power of .80 given an effect size of $f = .20$ (medium). Approval
468 and informed consent followed the same protocols as Experiment 1.

469 *3.1.2. Apparatus and stimuli*

470 The same stimuli and apparatus were used as in Experiment 1.

471 *3.1.3. Design and procedure*

472 The experimental design for Experiment 2 was a full factorial repeated measures design
473 with 2 within-subject factors: 3 x *retrocue latency* (short, long, non-cue) and 2 x *type of*
474 *array* (GA, NA). The task and procedure were the same as in Experiment 1, except for
475 the following: 1) the instructions explicitly emphasized that “if in the memory array two
476 items that share the same color appear, you must ignore these items as you will never be
477 asked for them”. 2) Given that grouped items acted as distractors, probe items were
478 always non-grouped elements of the memory array. 3) Experiment 2 consisted of 240
479 trials (40 trials per experimental condition), divided into two blocks of 120 trials with a
480 break between them. As in Experiment 1, all the experimental conditions were
481 randomly presented and response keys were counterbalanced across participants. No
482 feedback about the accuracy of the responses was given during experimental trials.

483 **3.2. Results**

484 The rejection criterion for invalid trials and the analysis strategy followed the same
485 rules specified in Experiment 1. The design of Experiment 2 was completely factorial,
486 so we performed a repeated-measures ANOVA on accuracy (% correct) scores and RTs
487 that included both factors.

488 *3.2.1. Accuracy (% correct)*

489 A 3x2 repeated measures ANOVA, with the within-subjects factors *retrocue latency*
490 (short, long, no-retrocue) and *array type* (GA, NGA) was performed on accuracy scores
491 (% correct). The main effect of the *retrocue latency* reached statistical significance F
492 (2,38) = 83.40; $p < .001$; $\eta^2p = .681$; $\beta = 1$. Multiple pairwise comparisons showed
493 differences between all retrocue conditions. Participants reached their best performance
494 in the short retrocue condition (90.2%), followed by long (79.6%) and no-retrocue
495 (70.1%) conditions respectively. The main effect of *array type* was also statistically
496 significant $F(1,39) = 25.69$; $p < .001$; $\eta^2p = .397$; $\beta = .99$. Accuracy for GA (81.6%)
497 was significantly better than accuracy for NGA (78.3%).
498 Last, the significant interaction effect between *retrocue latency* and *array type* $F(2,38)$
499 = 4.20; $p = .02$; $\eta^2p = .097$; $\beta = .722$ qualifies the main effects reported. Post-hoc
500 comparisons revealed that the better performance for GA only reached statistical
501 significance ($p < .001$) in no retrocue trials (73,4% vs 66.8%). No other effects reached
502 statistical significance. A summary of the accuracy results is shown in Figure 4.

503 **Fig. 4** Accuracy as a function of retrocue condition and grouped items in the array

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515 Accuracy (% correct) for arrays with and without grouped elements as a function of the
516 three retrocue conditions. NGA: non grouped arrays, GA: grouped arrays. The error
517 bars represent 1 SEM

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519 3.2.2. Reaction times

520 RTs were analyzed through a 3x2 repeated measures ANOVA, with the within-subjects
521 factors *retrocue latency* (short, long, no-retrocue) and *array type* (GA, NGA). The main

522 effect of the *retrocue latency* reached statistical significance $F(2,38) = 148.94$; $p <$
 523 $.001$; $\eta^2p = .792$; $\beta = 1$. Multiple pairwise comparisons carried out to break down this
 524 effect showed that participants were faster in responding to the short retrocue condition
 525 (742 ms), followed by long (926 ms) and no-retrocue (1211 ms) conditions respectively.
 526 No other main effects nor interactions were significant. A summary of the RTs for each
 527 condition can be seen in Table 2.

528 **Table 2.** Experiment 2 mean response times (SD) as a function of the type of array and
 529 retrocue latency.

		Array type	
		NGA	GA
Retrocue latency	Short	737 (292)	748 (302)
	Long	908 (332)	945 (377)
	No	1230 (552)	1193 (402)

530 GA: grouped array; NGA: non-grouped array. All response times are expressed in ms.

531 3.3. Interim discussion

532 Experiment 2 yielded an opposite pattern of results compared to Experiment 1 in both
 533 accuracy and RTs. The effect of the different retrocue conditions remained the same,
 534 but the critical change appeared when comparing performance between NGA and GA
 535 arrays. In Experiment 2 where participants were explicitly instructed to ignore grouped
 536 items, there was a clear benefit in terms of accuracy and RTs for GA, especially in the
 537 absence of a retrocue (as shown by the significant interaction between array type and
 538 retrocue condition). These results indicate that grouped items can be filtered out
 539 according to task goals, a result that agrees with those of Allon et al. (2019) who also
 540 found improved filtering performance in VWM when the irrelevant information was
 541 perceptually grouped. Thus, although perceptual grouping seems to have the capacity to
 542 automatically capture attention towards grouped items and bias the entry of information
 543 into VWM, it can also be inhibited following the task demands.

544 4. General Discussion

545 The purpose of the current study was to examine the effects of perceptual grouping
546 (color similarity) over the VWM performance, and the mechanisms behind this
547 performance improvement (e.g. Gao et al., 2016; Li et al., 2018; Peterson et al., 2015;
548 Peterson & Berryhill, 2013; Woodman et al., 2003; Zhang et al., 2016).

549 The results from Experiment 1 give support to the encoding bias hypothesis, at least
550 based on three convergent outcomes. First, although there is a general benefit in change
551 detection when some items can be grouped in the memory array, a closer look at this
552 effect shows that this benefit only appeared for GP and turned into a detrimental effect
553 when NGP were tested (see Fig. 2 left). If the presence of grouping items only affects
554 the memory task by allowing more efficient processing of the information to be stored
555 without any effect on the attentional resources allocated to each item, then we should
556 expect a similar benefit (and similar performance) for both grouped and non-grouped
557 probes (Corbett, 2017; Nassar et al., 2018). Second, the effect of the retrocue conditions
558 differed between GP and NGP. Particularly, these differences progressively increased as
559 the cue presentation interval became longer (see Fig. 2 right). This effect could be
560 explained by the weaker encoding of non-grouped items and the increased decay rate of
561 the memory trace over time (Barrouillet & Camos, 2012) or, alternatively, by a lower
562 probability of non-grouped items to be encoded due to the lower attentional resources
563 allocated to them (Anderson et al., 2013; Zhang & Luck, 2008). If the grouping effect
564 only affects the organization of the information without biasing attentional, we should
565 expect a similar effect of the different retrocue latencies for all the items in the memory
566 array. Third, the presence of grouped items in the memory array (GA trials) did not
567 improve change detection performance for NGP compared to NGA trials (see Fig. 2
568 left) as will be expected if perceptual grouping only organizes the visual information
569 without biasing the encoding of the items to be stored. Particularly, based on a pure

570 “chunking” hypothesis, grouped items should be treated as a single object (reducing the
571 number of effective items to be memorized to five) and, therefore, we would expect a
572 better overall performance in trials containing grouped items (GA) compared to trials
573 without grouped items (NGA). Instead, we found a mixed pattern of results depending
574 on the retrocue condition. In long-retrocue trials, the presence of grouped elements in
575 the memory array worsened change detection performance for NGP compared to arrays
576 without grouped elements, a decrease in performance that did not appear in short-
577 retrocue trials (see Fig. 2 left and Fig.3). This pattern of results could be explained by a
578 worse encoding of non-grouped items when other grouped items are present. In short-
579 retrocue trials, even if the non-grouped items are poorly encoded due to the presence of
580 grouped items, the aid of the retrocue presented when the iconic memory trace is still
581 available helped to maintain the performance level. However, in long-retrocue trials, the
582 poorer encoding and higher sensitivity to decay over time of the non-grouped elements
583 caused by the presence of grouped items led to a performance drop compared to trials in
584 which no grouped elements appeared. Surprisingly, this drop in performance did not
585 appear in the no-retrocue condition, a result that we expected to find according to the
586 encoding bias hypothesis (even to a greater extent than in long-retrocue trials). One
587 possible account for this absence of a significant effect in the no-retrocue condition
588 could be a floor effect in change detection performance. This explanation is supported
589 by the fact that a similar minimum performance was found in all the analyses conducted
590 in both experiments.

591 Taken together, the benefit in VWM performance seen in Experiment 1 seems to be
592 derived from a two-step process in which grouping cues are processed pre-attentionally
593 in the early stages of the visual stream, and impose a particular organization to the
594 scene. This organization, automatically directs the attention (and attentional resources)

595 to the grouped items due to an automatic feature-based attentional capture, leaving
596 fewer resources for processing the rest of the information (Edward Awh & Jonides,
597 2001; Heuer & Schubö, 2016; Oberauer, 2002; Treisman, 1982; Vecera, 1994). This
598 leads to an improvement for the grouped stimuli, with no performance boost or even a
599 detrimental effect for non-grouped items.

600 In Experiment 2, the main objective was to explore if the encoding bias found in
601 Experiment 1 could be voluntarily counteracted by the current task goals. To this end,
602 we performed the same CDT, but this time the participants were instructed to ignore
603 grouped items as they were irrelevant for the task. Accordingly, if the participants were
604 able to filter out the grouped items we should find an opposite pattern of results
605 compared to Experiment 1, with a better performance in those trials in which two
606 grouped items were part of the memory array (Allon et al., 2019; Sawaki & Luck, 2010,
607 2011). This opposite pattern of results is what we found in Experiment 2. Particularly,
608 the change detection performance increased in GA trials. However, a closer look at the
609 results revealed that this benefit was only significant when no retrocue was presented. A
610 likely explanation for this is that the presence of a cue in both short and long retrocue
611 conditions helped NGA trials to maintain a similar performance in the CDT by
612 signaling the target before it vanishes from VWM (Heuer & Schubö, 2016). On the
613 other hand, when no retrocue was available GA trials outperformed NGA trials as
614 participants were able to filter out the grouped items as irrelevant (see Figure 3).

615 Interestingly, when grouped items became irrelevant due to the task goals, the different
616 retrocue conditions (short and long) were equally effective regardless of the presence of
617 grouped elements in the array. This contrasts with Experiment 1, where long retro-cues
618 were less effective for NGP in GA (see Figure 2 right). Taken together, the evidence
619 from Experiment 2 supports the ability of the participants to voluntarily override the

620 attentional capture caused by the presence of grouped items according to the task goals.
621 This result agrees with those found with other grouping principles in similar tasks
622 (Allon et al., 2019), and contrasts with the effects found in time-based presentations
623 (Zupan & Watson, 2020).
624 Sawaki and Luck (2010) proposed a model of how salient singletons (i.e. stimuli that
625 contain unique feature values) capture attention in a stimulus-driven manner and the
626 degree to which top-down mechanism can attenuate or modulated this capture that is
627 fully congruent with the results of the present study. In their model, the authors posit
628 that salient items generate an attentional capture signal that, in the absence of top-down
629 control, automatically attracts attention (the bottom-up saliency hypothesis). This
630 automatic deployment can be avoided by a top-down active suppression process that is
631 contingent on the imposed task goals (the contingent involuntary orienting hypothesis).
632 This account can explain the results found in Experiment 1 (through an automatic
633 attentional capture provoked by the salience of previously grouped elements) and the
634 opposite pattern found in experiment 2 (due to the active suppression imposed by the
635 task instructions).
636 However, Even though our results support the encoding bias hypothesis derived from
637 the attentional capture generated by grouped items, we can not rule out that the two
638 mechanisms were working together at different stages of processing. It is feasible to
639 consider the early organization of the visual scene as a “chunking” process in which: 1)
640 items that share a common feature are treated as a single object, but 2) also lead to a
641 feature-based attentional capture that biases the encoding of information into VWM.
642 Last, although our study was not explicitly designed to investigate the limits of
643 information storing and maintenance in VWM, the results of Experiment 1 are
644 consistent with a flexible resources account of the working memory capacity and the

645 role of attention in the VWM performance. In a recent work, Emrich et al. (2017)
646 proposed a model of VWM limitations in which performance was determined by the
647 proportion of attentional resources allocated to the items during encoding. This account
648 offers a good explanation of both, the greater performance for GP and the differences in
649 retrocue effectiveness between GP and NGP as retrocue latencies became larger.
650 Specifically, the differences in change detection performance between grouped and non-
651 grouped items increased with retrocue latency, indicating that both memory
652 representations behave differently over time, a result that can be accounted from a
653 flexible resources perspective, in which the quality and resolution of memory
654 representations depend on the degree of attentional resources allocation (see also Bays
655 & Husain, 2008; Brady et al., 2011, 2016). The results of Experiment 2 were also
656 compatible with the attentional resources account, but given that grouped items were
657 never probed, we are not able to discern if these items received a lower amount of
658 attentional resources or were simply ignored and not encoded at all (which would lead
659 to chance level performance). Conversely, from a discrete resources point of view, the
660 storage of information is an all-or-none process, that either creates a representation at a
661 fixed level of detail or no representation at all (Zhang & Luck, 2008). According to this
662 model, once an item enters VWM, the level of precision and the strength of the memory
663 trace should be the same for all the information stored, so we would expect to find
664 similar differences between grouped and non-grouped probes in long and no retrocue
665 trials.

666 **5. Conclusions**

667 In the present study we found evidence supporting that the nature of the improvements
668 in VWM when part of the information can be grouped through perceptual grouping
669 cues, is not derived from optimized processing of the information to be remembered,

670 but from an attentional encoding bias that greatly favors the encoding, maintenance and
671 recovery of grouped items at the cost of worsening performance for the rest of the
672 information. Also, we found that this attentional encoding bias can be overridden by
673 top-down processes contingent on the current task goals. Overall, these two findings are
674 congruent with the dual model of attentional capture by salient items proposed by
675 Sawaki and Luck (2010), in which grouped items automatically generate an attend-to-
676 me signal independent of task-goals, but this signal can be overridden by top-down
677 suppression processes that prevent the actual capture of attention and filter out the
678 irrelevant information. Last, our study indirectly supports a flexible-resources account
679 of VWM storage based on the attentional resources allocated to the items, as shown by
680 the interactions between the different latencies of retrocue presentations and the type of
681 items cued.

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